

Efficient Algorithm for Resolving Scenarios of Complex Chromosomal Rearrangements

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Abstract

Complex Chromosomal Rearrangements are structural alterations changing the orientation, order, or copy number of genomic fragments. When such rearrangements amplify genetic material or affect homologous chromosomes, the sequence of derivative chromosomes may not be unambiguously determined based solely on the breakpoints of rearrangement and copy number of genome fragments demarcated by them. Moreover, *de novo* copies of genome fragments are devoid of small polymorphisms, preventing the phasing fragments originating from different parts of derivative chromosomes. Therefore, an efficient algorithm is needed to list all possible genome rearrangement scenarios given a multiset of breakpoints. The resulting enumeration of such scenarios can be subjected to downstream analyses explaining their molecular consequences.

Here we present a first efficient algorithm for listing all possible scenarios of Complex Chromosomal Rearrangements with minimal cardinality of derivative chromosomes. These rearrangements are represented by a model known as the Karyotype Graph. Each Eulerian Decomposition of Karyotype Graph represents a rearrangement scenario. Our algorithm enumerates all minimal decompositions of this graph in polynomial time delay complexity. We demonstrate the clinical applicability of our algorithm by inferring plausible scenarios to explain complex congenital rearrangements in patients harboring such alterations. The software package **KaryoTypeGraphs** implementing algorithms described in the article is available at <https://github.com/bposzewiecka/KaryoTypeGraphs>.

1 Introduction

Genetic background. Genome rearrangements alter the genome by breaking it into two or more loci and rejoining them in a different order, potentially causing fragment loss or amplification. The most common and well-studied rearrangements involve two breakpoints, including deletions, duplications, inversions, and translocations. Rearrangements with more than two breakpoints are classified as Complex Chromosomal Rearrangements (CCRs). Certain CCRs exhibit structural patterns linked to their formation mechanisms, such as DUP–TRP/INV–DUP (duplication–inverted triplication–duplication), characterized by inverted triplications interspersed with duplicated segments [6].

Over the last decade, CCRs characterized by a substantial number of breakpoints generated in a single mutational event resulting in derivative chromosomes without recurrent structure have been identified. These phenomena are collectively known as chromoanagenesis in the scientific literature. They are categorized into three groups based on the location of involved breakpoints and the mechanisms of their formation, namely chromothripsis, chromoplexy, and chromoanasythesis. Chromothripsis was initially described in cancer [20] and subsequently observed in patients with congenital disorders [12, 7, 24], as well as unaffected individuals [8]. It represents a single catastrophic event involving one chromosome shattering fragments of the genome, potentially resulting in the loss of DNA fragments. In this type of CCR, breakpoints cluster in one or a few chromosomal loci without any specific order and orientation. In the second type of massive CCR, called chromoplexy, breakpoint junctions can occur inter- and intra-chromosomally. This phenomenon was first observed in prostate cancer [4] and recently reported in a healthy female carrying two *de novo* CCRs

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involving six chromosomes, with a total of 137 breakpoint junctions [9]. The hallmark of the third type of massive CCR, termed chromoanasythesis, is a localized presence of copy number alterations along with copy-neutral fragments. This phenomenon in germline cells was first analyzed by Liu et al. [13], and recently described in the case of one proband from Nazaryan-Petersen et al. study [14]. Both chromothripsis and chromoplexy are explained by the non-homologous end joining mechanism, which repairs double-strand breaks during chromatin disruption, whereas chromoanasythesis is elucidated by replication-based mechanisms. Chromothripsis and chromoplexy events do not result in the amplification of genetic material. Hence, if they affect only one of the two homologous chromosomes, the order and orientation of rearranged fragments in derivative chromosomes can be determined without ambiguity. In the case of the chromoanasythesis, however, the structure of derivative chromosomes in most cases cannot be elucidated based solely on the rearrangement breakpoints. This is because the amplified fragments are longer than available long-reads data and lack small polymorphisms, making it impossible to phase amplified copies [16].

Modeling of CCRs. A model of CCR called Karyotype Graph (KG), has been proposed for cancer genomes [3] and can be straightforwardly applied to constitutional genome rearrangements. This model, however, does not provide information about the structure of the underlying derivative chromosomes, which hinders the comprehensive analysis of functional genomics changes caused by CCRs.

To address this issue, Aganezov et al. [3] formulated the Minimal Eulerian Decomposition Problem (MEDP), which aims to find a collection of linear and/or circular derivative chromosomes with minimal cardinality that can be inferred from KG. Moreover, by implementing the concept of omnitigs [21] for KGs, the authors introduced the Consistent Contig Covering Problem (CCCP) to recover unambiguous contigs that can be inferred from KGs. They have also proposed a polynomial time algorithm for solving this problem and successfully applied it to highly rearranged 17 prostate cancer samples. In chromoanasythesis, characterized by replication errors, the algorithm by Aganezov et al. [3] often produces very short unambiguous contigs. This limitation underscores the need for an efficient algorithm to enumerate all possible CCR scenarios.

Listing of all objects satisfying a specified property is one of the fundamental and extensively studied problems in combinatorics and graph theory. Examples of problems of this type include the enumeration of spanning trees [19], s-t paths [5], cycles [5], maximal cliques [22] and many others [23]. The output length of enumeration problems often grows exponentially with the size of the input, so the complexity of such problems is characterized in terms of both input and output size (output-sensitive). For enumeration algorithms there are several complexity classes, such as polynomial delay algorithms, where the time taken to generate two consecutive output solutions have to be polynomial in the input size.

Our contribution. We present the first efficient algorithm for listing all Minimal Eulerian Decompositions (MEDs) of a Karyotype Graph (KG) with a time delay of $O(\log^2(n) \cdot l)$, where n is the number of vertices and l the MED length. We apply this algorithm to enumerate rearrangement scenarios in a proband with congenital chromoanasythesis from Nazaryan-Petersen et al. [14] and to model a circular chromosome construct based on Grochowski et al. [10]. Additionally, we generate artificial KGs with varying edge counts to explore the asymptotic properties of rearrangement scenarios.

This paper is structured as follows. We define the KG and summarize key properties from the literature, showing that listing MEDs reduces to listing those of its connected components: Linearly Decomposable (LDKG) and Cyclically Decomposable (CDKG) Karyotype Graphs. For LDKGs, we propose an algorithm that reformulates the problem as listing specific MEDs in the Augmented Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph (ALDG), using a certificate to ensure solutions at each recursion node. We extend this approach to CDKGs by transforming them into ALDGs to generate building blocks for MED enumeration. Both algorithms are analyzed for time and space complexity. Finally, we demonstrate the algorithm’s applications and discuss future development and clinical implications.

2 Karyotype Graphs

Given an undirected multigraph $G = (V, E)$, let n be the number of vertices in G , and m be the number of its edges. Each vertex is uniquely represented by a number from the set $\{1, \dots, n\}$ and referred to as the *vertex number*. The multiplicity is a function $\mu : E \rightarrow \mathbb{N}_{\geq 0}$ encoding edges copy number. The sum of all multiplicities of a graph, $\sum_{e \in E} \mu(e)$, is referred to as l . A non-trivial graph is a graph where $l \neq 0$.

A *trail* is a sequence of adjacent ordered edges, where the number of occurrences of corresponding unordered edges is less than or equal to their multiplicities. For $s, t \in V$, an st -trail, denoted as $s \rightsquigarrow t$ is a trail where the first vertex is s and the last vertex is t . Let τ be a $t \rightsquigarrow u$ trail, we denote $G \setminus \tau$ as a graph G with multiplicities decremented by the number of occurrences of the corresponding edges in the trail τ . For an edge $\{u, v\}$, we denote $t \rightsquigarrow u \cdot (u, v)$ as the extension of the trail τ with the new edge $\{u, v\}$. A trail can be represented as a sequence of vertices, referred to as a *vertex representation* of a trail. Let us define the *canonical trail* as a trail whose *vertex representation* is lexicographically less than or equal to the *vertex representation* of the reversed trail, where the alphabet is the set of *vertex numbers*.

We use a CCR model named Karyotype Graph, and adhere to the nomenclature established in that work. Also definitions and lemmas from 1 to 8 are taken from the same work by Aganezov et al. [3].

Let the *reference genome* be a set of *reference chromosomes* described by their names and lengths. An *extremity* is defined by a *reference chromosome*, coordinate, and type (tail or head). Each reference chromosome can be partitioned into a set of non-overlapping fragments starting with a *tail extremity* and ending with *head extremity* and such elements are called *segments*. An unordered pair of *head* and *tail* extremities from the same segment representing a fragment of a chromosome is called a *segment edge*. An unordered pair of two *extremities* that is not a *segment edge* is called an *adjacency*. An *adjacency* formed by *head* and *tail extremity* from two consecutive *segments* is referred to as a *reference adjacency*. An *adjacency* that is not a *reference adjacency* forms a *breakpoint adjacency*.

Definition 1 (Karyotype Graph). *A Karyotype Graph (KG) is an undirected multigraph built upon the partition of the reference chromosomes into segments. A set of head and tail extremities of each segment establishes the vertices of the graph. The edges in this graph can be classified into two types: segment edges (encoding segments) and adjacency edges (encoding transitions between segments).*

Figure 1: **Karyotype Graph and corresponding rearranged genomes.** (A) The Karyotype Graph (KG) depicts two reference chromosomes. The first reference chromosome consists of segments A, B, C, and D, while the second one consists of segments E, F, G, and H. Segment edges are represented as solid lines, with color corresponding to the reference chromosomes. Reference adjacencies are shown as black dashed lines, and breakpoint adjacencies are shown as pink dashed lines. Edges with copy numbers different from one are labeled accordingly. The deleted segment (F, with copy number 0) is depicted in faded color. Extremities are shown in light green boxes, with telomeres depicted as squares and other extremities as circles. Tail and head extremities are marked with superscripted T and H letters, respectively. (B) Two scenarios of rearrangement (Eulerian Decompositions of KG) are shown, each consisting of two linear chromosomes corresponding to the Karyotype Graph from panel (A).

Definition 2 (Copy number excess). *Copy number excess $x(v)$ on vertex v is defined as the difference between the multiplicity of a segment edge containing v and the sum of the multiplicities of adjacencies incident to v , doubled in case of the adjacency loop (v, v) .*

Definition 3 (Telomere). *A vertex v with a copy number excess greater than 0 is referred as a telomere.*

Definition 4 (Eulerian Decomposition of KG). *A Karyotype Graph (KG) is called Decomposable (DKG) if it admits an Eulerian Decomposition, defined as a sequence of alternating segment-adjacency cycles and linear trails, starting and ending with a segment edge, where each edge appears exactly $\mu(e)$ times.*

Lemma 1. [2, 3, 15, 17] *A KG has an Eulerian Decomposition if and only if $\forall_{v \in V} x(v) \geq 0$.*

Lemma 2. [3] *Number of linear derivative chromosomes in DKG's Eulerian Decomposition is $\sum_{v \in E} \frac{x(v)}{2}$.*

Let us refer to k as the number of linear derivative chromosomes.

Definition 5 (Minimal Eulerian Decomposition of Decomposable Karyotype Graph). *The Minimal Eulerian Decomposition of DKG refers to the decomposition with the minimal cardinality.*

Lemma 3. [3] *For a DKG, the size of any Minimal Eulerian Decompositions is equal to:*

$$|D| = \sum_{v \in E} \frac{x(v)}{2} + |C_0|$$

where $|C_0|$ is the number of connected components of KG without telomeres.

Naturally, the problem of the enumeration of the MED of KG can be broken down into the enumeration of its connected components. Following the Lemma 3, each connected component without telomeres can be decomposed into a cycle, whereas connected components with telomeres decompose into a list of linear trails. Let us introduce the following definitions:

Definition 6 (Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph). *A Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph (LDKG) is a Decomposable Karyotype Graph with one connected component containing telomeres.*

Definition 7 (Cyclically Decomposable Karyotype Graph). *Cyclically Decomposable Karyotype Graph (CDKG) is Decomposable Karyotype Graph with one connected component without telomeres.*

An example of KG and its corresponding Minimal Eulerian Decompositions is presented in Fig. 1.

3 Minimal Ordered Eulerian Decompositions of Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph

Definition 8 (Minimal Ordered Eulerian Decomposition of LDKG). *The Minimal Ordered Eulerian Decomposition (MOED) of LDKG is a list of linear trails forming the Minimal Eulerian Decomposition of LDKG in their canonical representation and sorted in lexicographic order.*

Definition 9 (Augmented Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph based on LDKG). *An Augmented Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph (ALDKG) is build upon the LDKG by adding supplemental vertices S^T and S^H , the corresponding supplemental segment edge $\{S^T, S^H\}$ with multiplicity $2 \cdot k$, and the supplemental adjacency edge $\{S^T, S^T\}$ with multiplicity $k - 1$. Additionally, for every telomere T , an adjacency edge $\{T, S^H\}$ is created in ALDKG, with multiplicity equal to the copy number excess $x(T)$. The vertex number assigned to S^H is $2 \cdot m$ and to S^T is $2 \cdot m + 1$.*

The method of constructing ALDKG guarantees that it is connected and contains only one telomere S^T with copy number excess $x(S^T)$ equal to 2. Therefore, using Lemma 3 and the fact that LDKG is connected, the MOED of ALDKG consists of one linear trail. An example transformation of a LDKG into ALDKG is shown in Fig. 2.

Let us refine the definition of MOED for ALDKG by introducing an additional constraint requiring that the subsequence of a vertex representation of a trail, composed of all consecutive ordered edges starting with S^H , is sorted using the vertex number of the second element of the edge. With this redefinition, the enumeration of MOEDs in LDKG corresponds one-to-one with the enumeration of MOEDs of ALDKG. The MOED of LDKG is obtained from MOED of ALDKG by removing all edges incident to S^T and S^H from the only trail.

Figure 2: **Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph and corresponding Augmented Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph** (A) Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph with two ($k = 2$) linear derivative chromosomes (as the overall *copy number excess* of LDKG is equal to $\sum_{v \in E} x(v) = 4$). (B) Augmented Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph (ALDKG) build upon LDKG shown in panel (A). ALDKG is created by adding: (i) a supplemental segmental edge (S^T, S^H) with multiplicity $2 \cdot k = 4$, (ii) edges (T, S^H) with multiplicity 1 for all telomeres T from input graph (as 1 is the *copy number excess* of all telomeres in the input graph), (iii) a loop edge (S^T, S^T) with multiplicity $k - 1 = 1$.

3.1 Recursion certificates

Generating all possible MOEDs of ALDKG begins with exploring trails starting with the supplemental segmental edge (S^T, S^H) and it can be viewed as a recursive scheme, where the currently explored beginning of a trail $S^T \rightsquigarrow u$ is already fixed (initially $u = S^H$, where S^H is the supplementary head vertex). The process proceeds recursively by extending the trail $S^T \rightsquigarrow u$ at each step by adding two consecutive edges (adjacency and segmental) to the trail. For this purpose, each *good neighbor* v of u is explored. A vertex v is a *good neighbor* of u , if $\{u, v\}$ is an adjacency edge and the reduced graph $ALDKG' \equiv ALDKG \setminus (S^T \rightsquigarrow u) \cdot (u, v)$ does not contain more than one non-trivial connected component. For each *good neighbor* v , the recursion proceeds with the extended trail $S^T \rightsquigarrow w \equiv (S^T \rightsquigarrow u) \cdot (u, v) \cdot (v, w)$, where $\{v, w\}$ is a segmental edge and u is set to w . The recursive procedure terminates when all edges are used up. The recursion tree that is traversed while generating all possible MOEDs of ALDKG is presented in Fig. Supp 1 in the Appendix. Throughout the rest of the article, we use the term *node* when referring to the recursion tree, and *vertex* when referring to the input graph.

To make the recursion efficient, two auxiliary data structures are introduced: the *witness certificate* and the *connectivity certificate*. The former is used to derive some properties of MOEDs, which help to reduce the time complexity of finding the next *good neighbour* of a vertex v given the last *good neighbour* of the vertex in the recursion tree, while the latter enables efficient queries to prevent the creation of dead ends in the recursion tree.

Definition 10 (Witness certificate). *For a given LDKG the witness certificate is defined as any MOED of LDKG.*

The properties of the *witness certificate* are utilized to reduce the number of queries to the *connectivity certificate*. This is achieved by ensuring that the deletion of only one *adjacency edge* incident to the processed vertex can result in a dead end in the recursion tree.

Let us denote the i -th trail in the *witness certificate* as T_i and the first edge of T_1 as (t, u) . A positive answer to the question of whether some vertex v is a *good neighbor* of u can be given in the following cases:

1. Pair (u, v) is the second element of the trail T_1 .
2. Pair (u, v) or (v, u) is an element of a trail T_i different from T_1 (Fig. [Supp 2a](#), Fig. [Supp 2b](#)).
3. Pair (v, u) is an element of the trail T_1 (Fig. [Supp 2c](#)).
4. Pair (u, v) is an element of the trail T_1 and there exists another trail T_i with an edge containing vertex u (Fig. [Supp 2d](#), Fig. [Supp 2e](#)).
5. Pair (u, v) is an element of the trail T_1 and there exists another pair of vertices in T_1 containing u that is located further in T_1 (Fig. [Supp 2f](#), Fig. [Supp 2g](#)).

By applying appropriate transformations shown in Fig. [Supp 2](#) to the trails from the *witness certificate*, we can obtain another Minimal Eulerian Decomposition of DKG beginning with the segmental edge (t, u) , followed by the adjacency edge (u, v) and containing the same multiset of edges.

Therefore, the only case when the *witness certificate* cannot be used to confirm that the vertex v is a *good neighbor* of vertex u using simple transformations is when the pair (u, v) represents the last occurrence of u in trail T_1 and all of the other pairs containing u belong to trail T_1 but do not include the vertex v . Let us refer to such a vertex as an *uncertain vertex*.

Definition 11 (Connectivity certificate). *A connectivity certificate is a dynamic graph initially equal to ALDKG that enables the removal and addition of edges that form ALDKG.*

The *connectivity certificate* is used to check if the deletion of an edge from ALDKG results in the formation of two non-trivial connected components. The proposed data structure can be used for querying if, after removal of the edge in question, the vertices forming the edge are not isolated and are connected to the supplemental vertex S^H .

Lemma 4. *The connectivity certificate can be built in $O(\log^2(n) \cdot m)$ amortized time.*

Efficient implementation of the *connectivity certificate* can be achieved with a data structure based on Euler tour trees proposed by Holm et al. [11]. It enables queries for the connectivity of two vertices in a graph, as well as the addition and removal of edges in amortized $O(\log^2(n))$ time. The *connectivity certificate* is built by adding all edges in ALDKG to the aforementioned data structure. This can be done in $O(\log^2(n) \cdot m)$ amortized time, since the number of edges not incident to supplemental vertices is at most m and the number of edges incident to supplemental vertices does not exceed $[2.5 \cdot m]$.

An additional data structure called *edge index*, is a dictionary storing, for every vertex, a list of vertices incident to it by adjacency edges, along with their multiplicity. The *edge index* can be implemented using AVL tree [1], which enables adding, removing and querying for entries, as well as locating the next entry in $O(\log(m))$ time, where m is the number of entries. The dictionary is built by enumerating all edges of KG and adding appropriate entries to it. This can be done in $O(\log(m) \cdot m)$ time.

3.2 Traversal of the recursion tree

The *connectivity certificate* is employed to: (1) ensure the existence of at least one *good neighbor* of the currently processed vertex u (there are no dead ends in the recursion tree), (2) locate the next *good neighbor* of the currently processed vertex u and save space by keeping only one in the recursion stack instead of a the list of vertices, (3) quickly skip nodes with only one *good neighbor* of u .

At least one good neighbor of u . Throughout the traversal of a recursion tree the invariant is that the *connectivity certificate* is connected, which guarantees the existence of at least one MOED that extends the currently processed trail $S^T \rightsquigarrow u$. This, in turn, ensures that at least one *good neighbor* exists for the processed vertex u .

Next good neighbor of u . The next *good neighbor* is retrieved from the *vertex index* using ordering based on their *vertex numbers*. This ensures a reduction in the space of the recursion stack and guarantees that the produced MOEDs will be returned in lexicographic order, where the alphabet is a set of *vertex representations* of trails.

Lemma 5. *Given a trail $S^T \rightsquigarrow w = (S^T \rightsquigarrow u) \cdot (u, v) \cdot (v, w)$ and its connectivity certificate C , the next good neighbor (in terms of ordering using vertex indices) can be found in $O(\log^2(n))$ amortized time.*

Proof. If $u = S^H$ there is no next good neighbour. Otherwise, edges (u, v) and (v, w) are added to C . Then, the next entry after (u, v) is retrieved from the *edge index*. If such an entry exists, it is verified if it is a *good neighbor* using C by removing edge (u, v) and the segmental edge with vertex v and checking if vertex v is connected to S^T . If the answer is positive, the vertex is the next *good neighbour* and the removed vertices are added to the certificate. Otherwise, the next vertex incident to u is returned (if such exists), as only one vertex can be the *uncertain vertex*. All operations concerning the *edge index* take $O(\log(m))$ time and operations concerning C take $O(\log^2(n))$ amortized time.

Lemma 6. *Given the current node of the recursion tree and the connectivity certificate C for its trail $S^T \rightsquigarrow u$, the certificates for the parent or a child of the node can be computed in $O(\log^2(n))$ amortized time.*

Proof. Let $(S^T \rightsquigarrow u')$ be a trail in the parent node, where v' is a *good neighbor* of u' . Then, the connectivity certificate for a child can be obtained by removing edges (u', v') and (v', w') from C .

Let $S^T \rightsquigarrow w = (S^T \rightsquigarrow u) \cdot (u, v) \cdot (v, w)$ be the connectivity certificate C in the child node. The connectivity certificate for the parent node is obtained by adding edges (u, v) and (v, w) to C . All these operations take $O(\log^2(n))$ amortized time. The *edge index* should be updated accordingly, which takes $O(\log(m))$ time.

Theorem 1. *Given an ALDKG, all its MOEDs can be listed in lexicographic order (where the alphabet is a set of edge representations of trails) without duplicates with an $O(\log^2(n) \cdot l)$ time cost per solution. The initial setup time is $O(\log^2(n) \cdot m)$, and the space complexity required for the algorithm is $O(\log(m) \cdot l)$.*

By the definition of a *good neighbor*, given a partial trail $S^T \rightsquigarrow u$, a simple induction shows that the algorithm will generate all MOEDs having $S^T \rightsquigarrow u$ as a prefix. No MOEDs will be listed twice for the same reason. Suppose, by contradiction, that there exists a MOED that is not outputted. Let $S^T \rightsquigarrow u$ be the recursion node that fails to generate a child. By the definition of a *good neighbor*, this is a contradiction, as using it we find all v that can extend to obtain $S^T \rightsquigarrow u \cdot (u, v)$

Let m_1 , and m_2 be MOEDs and let $S^T \rightsquigarrow u$ be their common longest prefix of edges in the trail, followed by the next edge. Let $S^T \rightsquigarrow u \cdot (u, v_1)$ and $S^T \rightsquigarrow u \cdot (u, v_2)$ be the respective trails, where $v_1 \neq v_2$. Due to the fact that prefixes of MOEDs are always extended by a pair of edges and the second one is a segmental edge determined unambiguously based on the first adjacency edge, the $\{u, v_1\}$ and $\{u, v_2\}$ are adjacency edges. Without loss of generality, let us assume that $v_1 < v_2$. The recursion traverses child elements of a parent in the order of their *vertex number* so m_1 will be generated before m_2 , ensuring that all MOEDs will be returned in lexicographic order (where the alphabet is a set of edge representations of trails).

Since the algorithm spends $O(\log^2(n))$ amortized time in each node of the recursion tree, and there are l nodes for each solution, we get $O(\log^2(n) \cdot l)$ amortized time per solution. The space complexity is $O(\log(m) \cdot l)$, as the recursion stack can be at most $O(l)$ long and the memory per node is constant, the AVL tree used in $O(m)$, and dynamic graph proposed by Holm et al. [11] is $O(\log(m) \cdot m)$.

4 Minimal Eulerian Decompositions of Cyclically Decomposable Karyotype Graph

Definition 12 (Augmented Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph based on Cyclically Decomposable Karyotype Graph). *Augmented Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph (ALDKG) build upon the Cyclically Decomposable Karyotype Graph (CDKG) created by:*

- removing segmental edge with the lowest vertex number. Let $\{A^T, A^H\}$ be such an edge and $\mu(A)$ be the multiplicity of the edge $\{A^T, A^H\}$,
- adding two segmental edges $\{A^T, A_i^H\}$ and $\{A_i^T, A^H\}$ with multiplicity $\mu(A)$,
- adding a supplemental segment edge $\{S^T, S^H\}$ with multiplicity $2 \cdot \mu(A)$,
- adding a supplemental adjacency edge $\{S^T, S^T\}$ with multiplicity $\mu(A) - 1$,

- adding adjacency edges $\{A_t^H, S^H\}$ and $\{S^H, A_h^T\}$ with multiplicity $\mu(A)$.

Every *edge representation* of a MED of CDKG starting with edge (A^T, A^H) can be divided into subtrails demarcated by edge $\{A^T, A^H\}$. These trails are of three types: (i) those starting and followed by (A^T, A^H) or (A^H, A^T) , referred to as **tail-head** subtrails, (ii) those starting with (A^T, A^H) and followed by (A^H, A^T) , referred to as **head-head** subtrails, (iii) those starting with (A^H, A^T) and followed by (A^T, A^H) , referred to as **tail-tail** subtrails. Mind that, the subsequent trail of the last subtrail is defined as the first subtrail, maintaining the cyclic structure.

Notice that the number of head-head and tail-tail subtrails is equal, since the MED is cyclic and each subtrail of head-head and tail-tail subtrails changes the orientation of the starting edge $\{A^T, A^H\}$ of consecutive subtrails. Let the number of head-head and tail-tail subtrails will be m (m is less or equal to $\mu(A)/2$).

An ALDKG constructed from a CDKG is used to enumerate multisets of trails. Each element in the list, obtained by removing edges incident to S^T and S^H , corresponds to one of three subtrail types: it belongs to tail-head subtrails if it starts at (A_h^T, A^H) and ends at (A^T, A_t^H) ; to head-head subtrails if it starts and ends at (A_h^T, A^H) ; and to tail-tail subtrails if it starts and ends at (A^T, A_t^H) .

To enumerate all minimal building block lists forming a MED of CDKG, starting with edge (A^T, A^H) and ending with an edge where A^T is the second element, we consider two types of building blocks: (1) tail-head subtrails, and (2) concatenations of a head-head subtrail, any number of tail-head subtrails, and a tail-tail subtrail. The enumeration involves: assigning tail-tail subtrails to head-head subtrails; dividing tail-head subtrails into those forming standalone blocks and those placed between head-head and tail-tail subtrails; further partitioning the latter into multisets of cardinality m ; generating multisets of m words via concatenation; and assigning these words to the initial subtrail assignments. The first and last problem are equivalent to the problem of enumerating all assignments between elements of two multisets with the same

Figure 3: **Cyclically Decomposable Karyotype Graph and corresponding Augmented Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph** (A) Cyclically Decomposable Karyotype Graph (CDKG). (B) Augmented Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph (ALDKG) built upon CDKG shown in panel (A). ALDKG is created by removing edge $\{A^T, A^H\}$ with multiplicity $\mu(A) = 3$ and adding (i) two segmental edges $\{A^T, A_t^H\}$ and $\{A_h^T, A^H\}$ with the multiplicity $\mu(A) = 3$, (ii) a supplemental segmental edge (S^T, S^H) with multiplicity $2 \cdot \mu(A) = 6$, (iii) a supplemental adjacency edge $\{S^T, S^T\}$ with multiplicity $\mu(A) - 1 = 2$, (iv) adjacency edges $\{A_t^H, S^H\}$ and $\{S^H, A_h^T\}$ with multiplicity $\mu(A) = 3$.

cardinality (See A 1.1). The second and third problems can be jointly solved as the problem of enumerating divisions of a multiset into a multiset of $m + 1$ multisets (See A 1.2). To solve the fourth problem, for each element t with multiplicity $\mu(t)$, we generate a sequence of $\mu(t)$ lexicographically ordered concatenations of t . Elements from the Cartesian product of these sequences are then joined and flattened. The enumeration accounts for head-head and tail-tail subtrails, which can be output in both directions if non-palindromic. This procedure runs in linear time per solution.

All MEDs of CDKG must be assembled from these building blocks while avoiding duplicate MEDs caused by cyclic rotations. In stringology, the term necklace refers to the lexicographically smallest string in a rotation-equivalence class. Sawada [18] introduced an algorithm for generating necklaces with fixed symbol counts in constant amortized time, which can be directly applied to generate MEDs of CDKG from the previously defined building blocks. All enumeration procedures, except for MOED enumeration, have linear time delay per output. Thus, the overall enumeration of CDKG has a time delay of $O(\log^2(n) \cdot l)$, where n is the number of vertices in the DKG and l its length.

5 Reconstructing Scenarios of Complex Chromosomal Rearrangements

We have applied our enumeration algorithm for listing rearrangement scenarios for the case P5513_206 from Nazaryan-Petersen et al. study [14]. Our algorithm found 17 possible scenarios of Complex Chromosomal Rearrangements presented in this study. KG with breakpoints described in this case and corresponding rearranged genomes are presented in panel A of Figure Supp 3.

As a second validation of our algorithm on clinical data we have confirmed the structure of circular chromosome construct described in Grochowski et al. study [10] using breakpoints found therein. Corresponding KG and one circular derivative chromosome is presented in panel B of Figure Supp 3.

To evaluate the asymptotic properties of the number of generated MOEDs, as well as the ratio of the number of MOEDs to the number of KG decompositions into trails and cycles produced using the naive procedure given the size of the input KG, two sets of artificial KG has been created. Both of them are built of one reference chromosome with n segmental edges connected with adjacency edges. Each artificial KG has two telomeres with copy number excess equal to 1. In the first set every odd segment edge has multiplicity 2 and pairs of vertices of breakpoint adjacencies are assigned to each other randomly. In the second set sum of the multiplicities of all segmental edges is equal to $\lfloor 1.5 \cdot n \rfloor$. Reference edges join n segmental edges, and remaining $\lfloor 0.5 \cdot n \rfloor$ edges are assigned randomly to segments. The corresponding adjacency edges are connected randomly. For the simulation we have used n from the set $\{10, 15, 20, 25, 30\}$ and for each of these values we have conducted 100 simulations. Panels (a) and (c) in Figure Supp 4 present the number of MOEDs given the number of segmental edges used in simulations, for first and second type of *in-silico* simulations, respectively. Both figures show that these quantities follow exponential growth. Panels (b) and (d) in Figure Supp 4 present boxplots of the ratio of the number of MOEDs to the number of decomposition of KG to trails and cycles generated using naive procedure. Median value for all simulated datasets is contained in an interval (0.19, 0.34).

The software package **KaryoTypeGraphs** implementing algorithms described in this article has been written in Python and is available at <https://github.com/bposzewiecka/KaryoTypeGraphs>.

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Appendix

A 1.1 Enumerating Assignments Between Equal-Cardinality Multisets

Let the first multiset be A , and the second multiset be B , and let multiplicities of $a \in A$ and $b \in B$ be $\mu_A(a)$ and $\mu_B(b)$, respectively. To provide an assignment from the multiset A to the multiset B , we have to construct a function f that for each element $a \in A$ returns a multiset of elements from B with cardinality $\mu(a)$, such that each element $b \in B$ has multiplicity of $\mu_B(b)$ in the multiset $\bigcup_{a \in A} f(a)$.

Let us define the order of multisets A as the lexicographic order on sorted sequences of elements $a \in A$ from the multiset that occur exactly $\mu(a)$ times in the sequence. Using this order, we can compare lexicographically the assignments defined above, assuming we have defined order on elements from multisets A and B .

A non-increasing suffix of assignment f of multiset A of ordered elements $\{1, \dots, n\}$ to multiset B of ordered elements is a sequence of $(f(i), f(i+1), \dots, f(n))$ that for each $j \in \{i+1, n\}$ satisfies the inequality $\min(f(j-1)) \geq \max(f(j))$ for $i < n$ or a single-element sequence $(f(n))$. The non-increasing suffix is the greatest element from all suffixes built from the same multiset.

Here we present the method of the enumeration of all assignments in the lexicographic order. First, we generate the least element from all possible assignments. This assignment can be built by assigning iteratively for each $i \in A$ smallest element from B that can be used. Then, repeatedly, we construct the next assignment in the previously defined order until the longest possible non-increasing suffix is returned.

To generate the next assignment f_{next} from f we have to find the longest non-increasing suffix of f . Let $(f(i), f(i+1), \dots, f(n))$ be such a suffix. Then $f(i-1)$ contains an element that is smaller than the greatest element of $f(i)$, as otherwise it will be contained in the longest non-increasing suffix. To produce $f_{next}(i-1)$ we have to find in $f(i-1)$ an element satisfying this condition and switch it with the smallest element from the non-increasing suffix that is greater than it. Let the index of this element in $f(i-1)$ be k . Elements from $f(i-1)$ with indices greater than k and the entire non-increasing suffix are sorted. The fragment from $f(i-1)$ with indices greater than k is replaced by the fragment from the sorted subsequence containing $\mu_A(i-1) - k$ elements with the minimal possible starting index with value greater or equal to $f(i-1)[k]$. The non-increasing suffix is then replaced by remaining elements. All these operations can be done in linear time.

A 1.2 Enumerating Multiset Divisions into m Submultisets

Let A be the input multiset and B be the multiset with cardinality m . To enumerate all possible multisets B , for each $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ and each $k \in A$ we should assign a multiplicity of i_k , in a way that $\sum_{i \in \{1, \dots, m\}} \mu(i_k) = \mu_A(k)$. Multiplicities are assigned iteratively for each $k \in A$, for entries sharing common prefix in non-increasing order. This procedure prevents the generation of duplicated multisets. It's obvious that this enumeration procedure has a linear time delay per output.

Supplementary Figures

Figure Supp 1: **Scheme of recursion tree for enumerating Minimal Ordered Eulerian Decompositions of Augmented Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph.** τ_i denotes i -th trail in the MOED of LDKG corresponding to ALDKG. The recursion begins by extending a trail formed by a single supplemental segmental ordered edge (S^T, S^H) with a vertex that is a telomere with the lowest *vertex number* in the corresponding LDKG. The top tree is built of paths representing all feasible choices of τ_1 and its leaves on the first dashed level correspond bijectively to trails τ_1 . All leaves of the top tree are the roots of the recursion tree for unary nodes that generate paths corresponding to visiting vertices S^H and S^T and continuing the extension of a trail with a vertex that is a telomere with the lowest *vertex number* in corresponding LDKG that has not been used. Traversing the unary node chain produces a fragment of a trail equal to $(t_1, S^H), (S^H, S^T), (S^T, S^T), (S^T, S^H), (S^H, t_2)$, there t_1 and t_2 are telomeres in the corresponding LDKG. Leaves in the third dashed levels correspond bijectively to trails τ_2 , and so on. Nodes b, c, d correspond to possible choices of τ_1 , whereas nodes e and f correspond to possible choices of τ_2 where τ_1 is represented by a path ending with node b (respectively g , when τ_1 is represented by c , next h and i , when τ_1 is represented by path ending with node d). Nodes from the last dashed line (from p to w) correspond bijectively to a sequence of trails τ_1, \dots, τ_k that form MOED of LDKG. The recursion ends by extending the trail with an adjacency edge incident to S^H and the supplemental segmental ordered edge (S^H, S^T) .

(a) Transformation for $(u, v) \in T_i, i \neq 1$.

(b) Transformation for $(v, u) \in T_i, i \neq 1$.

(c) Transformation for $(v, u) \in T_1$.

(d) Transformation for $(u, v) \in T_1, \exists(u, x) \in T_i, i \neq 1$.

(e) Transformation for $(u, v) \in T_1, \exists(x, u) \in T_i, i \neq 1$.

(f) Transformation for $(u, v) \in T_1, \exists(u, x) \in T_1$, such that (x, u) has greater position in T_1 than (u, v) .

(g) Transformation for $(u, v) \in T_1, \exists(x, u) \in T_1$, such that (x, u) has greater position in T_1 than (u, v) .

Figure Supp 2: Transformation of the *witness certificate* showing that the vertex v is a *good neighbor* of vertex u , given certain locations of other edges containing u . Segmental edges are depicted as solid lines, while adjacency edges are depicted as dashed lines. Arrows indicate the ordering of vertices in the edges which is preserved during transformations.

Figure Supp 3: **Two Karyotype Graphs and corresponding rearranged genomes for cases taken from clinical literature (A)** Linearly Decomposable Karyotype Graph and corresponding seventeen rearranged genomes for the case P5513.206 from the Nazaryan-Petersen et al. study [14]. **(B)** Cyclically Decomposable Karyotype Graph and corresponding circular chromosome build using breakpoints found in the case presented in Grochowski et al. study [10].

(a) Number of MOEDs given the number of segmental edges in simulations of the first type.

(b) Ratio of the number of MOEDs to the number of decomposition of KG to trails and cycles generated using naive procedure given the number of segmental edges in simulations of the first type.

(c) Number of MOEDs given the number of segmental edges in simulations of the second type.

(d) Ratio of the number of MOEDs to the number of decomposition of KG to trails and cycles generated using naive procedure given the number of segmental edges in simulations of the second type.

Figure Supp 4: **Asymptotic properties of the number of MOEDs in simulated datasets.** Panels (a) and (b) present simulation of the first type where KG has two telomeres with copy number excess equal to 1 and even segmental edges have multiplicity 2. Panels (c) and (d) present simulation of the second type where KG has two telomeres with copy number excess equal to 1 and the sum of the multiplicities of segmental edges is equal $\lfloor 1.5 \cdot \#segmental_edges \rfloor$ and $\lfloor 0.5 \cdot \#segmental_edges \rfloor$ of them are assigned randomly to segments.